

Tagungsbeitrag zu:
Jahrestagung der DBG, Kommission IV
Titel der Tagung: Böden eine endliche
Ressource
Veranstalter: DBG, 05.-13.09.2009, Bonn
Berichte der DBG (nicht begutachtete
Online-Publikation)
<http://www.dbges.de>

¹³C fractionation in transformations at the interface between roots, microorganisms, soil organic matter and soil respiration

Martin Werth¹ and Yakov Kuzyakov²

Keywords: ¹³C natural abundance, ¹³C fractionation, root respiration, microbial respiration, preferential substrate utilization, CO₂ partitioning

Introduction

Natural variations of the ¹³C/¹²C ratio have been frequently used over the last three decades to trace C sources and fluxes between plants, microorganisms, and soil. Most of these studies have used the natural ¹³C labelling approach, i.e. natural δ¹³C variation after C₃ – C₄ vegetation changes. In this mini-review, we focus on ¹³C fractionation in processes at the interface between roots, microorganisms, and soil: root respiration, microbial respiration, formation of dissolved organic carbon by root exudation, as well as microbial uptake and utilization of soil organic matter (SOM).

Root respiration

Based on literature data (Wedin et al., 1995; Klumpp et al., 2005; Schnyder and Lattanzi, 2005; Werth et al., 2006; Werth and Kuzyakov, 2006; Gessler et al., 2007;

Larsen et al., 2007; Werth and Kuzyakov, 2009), we estimated that, on average, the roots of C₃ and C₄ plants are ¹³C enriched compared to shoots by -1.2±0.6‰ and -0.3±0.4‰, respectively. A very few studies showed that CO₂ released by root respiration was ¹³C depleted by about +2.7±1.8‰ for C₃ plants and +1.3±2.4‰ for C₄ plants compared to root tissue. This urgently calls for further studies to reliably estimate ¹³C fractionation by root respiration.

Microbial utilization

In soils developed under C₃ vegetation (Qian and Doran, 1996; Qian et al., 1997; Liang et al., 1999; Santruckova et al., 2000; Gregorich et al., 2000; Formánek and Ambus, 2004; Hamer et al., 2004; Kristiansen et al., 2004; Pelz et al., 2005; Stevenson et al., 2005; Piao et al., 2006; Dijkstra et al., 2006; Werth et al., 2006; Crow et al., 2006; Boström et al., 2007; Werth and Kuzyakov, 2009), the microbial biomass was ¹³C enriched by -1.2±2.6‰ and microbial CO₂ was ¹³C enriched by -0.7±2.8‰ compared to SOM (Fig. 1). This discrimination pattern suggests preferential utilization of a ¹³C-enriched soil fraction by microorganisms, but a respiration of lighter compounds from this fraction. Preferential consumption of easily decomposable substrates and less negative δ¹³C values were common for substances with low C/N ratios. For C₄ soils (Santruckova et al., 2000; Dijkstra et al., 2006), preferential substrate utilization was less important than for C₃ soils. This is because, here, microbial respiration strictly followed kinetics, i.e. microorganisms incorporated heavier carbon (Δ = -1.1‰) and respired lighter carbon (Δ = +1.1‰) than SOM (Fig. 1).

¹ Universität Ulm
Institut für Systematische Botanik und Ökologie
martin.werth@uni-ulm.de

² Universität Bayreuth
Agrarökosystemforschung
kuzyakov@uni-bayreuth.de

Fig. 1: ^{13}C discrimination processes between soil organic matter (SOM) and the soil carbon pools: dissolved organic carbon (DOC), microbial biomass (MB), and SOM-derived CO_2 for C_3 and C_4 soils.

Fig. 2: Soil organic matter $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ vs. mean annual temperature (MAT) (a) and soil-derived CO_2 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ vs. mean annual precipitation (MAP) (b) from sites with C_3 vegetation. The solid line shows the regression line, the dashed lines show the 95% confidence interval of the regression. For references see the beginning of this section.

Temperature and precipitation had no significant effect on the ^{13}C fractionation in these processes in C_3 soils. Increasing temperature and decreasing precipitation led, however, to increasing $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of soil C pools (Fig. 2).

CO_2 partitioning

In the framework of standard isotope mixing models, we calculated CO_2 partitioning using the natural ^{13}C labelling approach at a vegetation change from C_3 to C_4 plants. A root-derived fraction of 25%, 50%, and 75% to total soil respiration was assumed. Disregarding any ^{13}C fractionation processes (Eq. (13)), the calculated results deviated by between 2% and 7% from the presumed fractions (Fig. 3). Accounting for fractionation processes in the standard errors of the C_4 source pool and the mixing pool (Eq. (13) Fract. in SE) did not improve the exactness of the partitioning results; rather, it doubled the standard errors of the CO_2 pools. Including ^{13}C fractionations directly into the mass balance equations (Eq. (20) Fract. in SE) reproduced the CO_2 partitioning exactly.

Fig. 3: Partitioning of soil CO_2 efflux into root-derived (grey) and SOM-derived (white) carbon. Natural ^{13}C labelling was used by planting a C_4 plant on soil developed under C_3 vegetation. Root-derived respiration from the C_4 plant (root respiration and rhizomicrobial respiration) was assumed to contribute 25%, 50%, and 75% to the CO_2 efflux. ^{13}C fractionation between root-derived sources and CO_2

was either disregarded (Eq. (13)), accounted for in the standard error of the C_4 'end member' and the mixing pool (Eq. (13) Fract. in SE), or accounted for in the partitioning equation and in the standard error of the C_4 'end member' and the mixing pool (Eq. (20) Fract. in SE). Standard errors of the contributions are shown in the centre of the columns with their values below.

Conclusions

Most C transformations such as root respiration, formation of DOC, microbial utilization of soil organic matter as well as microbial respiration are correlated with significant changes of C isotopic signatures compared to that of the C source. The ^{13}C fractionation within individual steps of C transformation is highly variable and is comparable with the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ difference between the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of 'end members' commonly used in natural ^{13}C labelling studies. This makes it inappropriate to accept literature data about possible changes of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ within the processes. Rather, the discrimination should be measured for the specific conditions of the experiment.

Simple calculations of partitioning errors in studies based on the natural ^{13}C labelling approach showed high uncertainties of the results. This reflects small differences of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values between the 'end members', natural variation of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values within the 'end members' and the mixed pool, uncertainties of ^{13}C fractionation, and preferential substrate utilization. This calls for caution in interpreting the results obtained using the natural ^{13}C labelling approach.

References

Boström, B., Comstedt, D., Ekblad, A., 2007. Isotope fractionation and ^{13}C enrichment in soil profiles during the decomposition of soil organic matter. *Oecologia* 153, 89-98.

Crow, S.E., Sulzman, E.W., Rugh, W.D., Bowden, R.D., Lajtha, K., 2006. Isotopic

analysis of respired CO_2 during decomposition of separated soil organic matter pools. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 38, 3279-3291.

Dijkstra, P., Ishizu, A., Doucett, R., Hart, S.C., Schwartz, E., Menyailo, O.V., Hungate, B.A., 2006. ^{13}C and ^{15}N natural abundance of the soil microbial biomass. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 38, 3257-3266.

Formánek, P., Ambus, P., 2004. Assessing the use of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ natural abundance in separation of root and microbial respiration in a Danish beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) forest. *Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry* 18, 1-6.

Gessler, A., Keitel, C., Kodama, N., Weston, C., Winters, A.J., Keith, H., Grice, K., Leuning, R., Farquhar, G.D., 2007. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of organic matter transported from the leaves to the roots in *Eucalyptus delegatensis*: Short-term variations and relation to respired CO_2 . *Functional Plant Biology* 34, 692-706.

Gregorich, E.G., Liang, B.C., Drury, C.F., MacKenzie, A.F., McGill, W.B., 2000. Elucidation of the source and turnover of water soluble and microbial biomass carbon in agricultural soils. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 32, 581-587.

Hamer, U., Dalhus, W., Marschner, B., Schulte, U., Gleixner, G., 2004. Isotopic ^{13}C fractionation during the mineralisation of organic substrates. In: Hamer, U. (Ed.), Priming effects of dissolved organic substrates on the mineralisation of lignin, peat, soil organic matter and black carbon determined with ^{14}C and ^{13}C isotope techniques. PhD thesis at the Ruhr-Universität Bochum, Germany, pp. 129-150.

Klumpp, K., Schäufele, R., Lötscher, M., A., L.F., Feneis, W., Schnyder, H., 2005. C-isotope composition of CO_2 respired by shoots and roots: fractionation during dark respiration? *Plant, Cell & Environment* 28, 241-250.

Kristiansen, S.M., Brandt, M., Hansen, E.M., Magid, J., Christensen, B.T., 2004. ^{13}C signature of CO_2 evolved from incubated

- maize residues and maize-derived sheep faeces. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 36, 99-105.
- Larsen, T., Gorissen, A., Krogh, P.H., Ventura, M., Magid, J., 2007. Assimilation dynamics of soil carbon and nitrogen by wheat roots and Collembola. *Plant and Soil* 295, 253-264.
- Liang, B.C., Gregorich, E.G., MacKenzie, A.F., 1999. Short-term mineralization of maize residues in soils as determined by carbon-13 natural abundance. *Plant and Soil* 208, 227-232.
- Pelz, O., Abraham, W.-R., Saurer, M., Siegwolf, R., Zeyer, J., 2005. Microbial assimilation of plant-derived carbon in soil traced by isotope analysis. *Biology and Fertility of Soils* 41, 153-162.
- Piao, H.C., Zhu, J.M., Liu, G.S., Liu, C.Q., Tao, F.X., 2006. Changes of natural ^{13}C abundance in microbial biomass during litter decomposition. *Applied Soil Ecology* 33, 3-9.
- Qian, J.H., Doran, J.W., 1996. Available carbon released from crop roots during growth as determined by carbon-13 natural abundance. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 60, 828-831.
- Qian, J.H., Doran, J.W., Walters, D.T., 1997. Maize plant contributions to root zone available carbon and microbial transformations of nitrogen. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 29, 1451-1462.
- Santruckova, H., Bird, M.I., Lloyd, J., 2000. Microbial processes and carbon-isotope fractionation in tropical and temperate grassland soils. *Functional Ecology* 14, 108-114.
- Schnyder, H., Lattanzi, F.A., 2005. Partitioning respiration of C3-C4 mixed communities using the natural abundance ^{13}C approach - testing assumptions in a controlled environment. *Plant Biology* 7, 592-600.
- Stevenson, B.A., Kelly, E.F., McDonald, E.V., Busacca, A.J., 2005. The stable carbon isotope composition of soil organic carbon and pedogenic carbonates along a bioclimatic gradient in the Palouse region, Washington State, USA. *Geoderma* 124, 37-47.
- Wedin, D.A., Tieszen, L.L., Dewey, B., Pastor, J., 1995. Carbon isotope dynamics during grass decomposition and soil organic matter formation. *Ecology* 76, 1383-1392.
- Werth, M., Kuzyakov, Y., 2006. Assimilate partitioning affects ^{13}C fractionation of recently assimilated carbon in maize. *Plant and Soil* 284, 311-325.
- Werth, M., Kuzyakov, Y., 2009. Three-source partitioning of CO_2 efflux from maize field soil by ^{13}C natural abundance. *Journal of Plant Nutrition and Soil Science* 172, 487-499.
- Werth, M., Subbotina, I., Kuzyakov, Y., 2006. Three-source partitioning of CO_2 efflux from soil planted with maize by ^{13}C natural abundance fails due to inactive microbial biomass. *Soil Biology & Biochemistry* 38, 2772-2781.